

Crafting an Xtended apprenticeship for the future

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The proposal seeks to present the experience of an ongoing project regarding the use of XR technologies for the preservation of traditional crafts techniques and the enhancement of the process of apprenticeship. Creative@Hubs: Holistic networking of creative industries via hubs, a GR-IT Interreg project, aims at safeguarding, valorising, and passing on the quality of craftsmanship with the utilisation of digital technologies in order to guarantee a constructive future for crafts.

Figure 1 Creative@Hubs concept diagram

Crafts constitute a major part in the shaping of collective history and culture; in constructing collective identity; in strengthening the sense of belonging; and in relating us to past times and the generations that lived before us. They showcase the interpenetrating relationship between material culture and human beings. Artefacts and traditional objects are cultural products as they accumulate social, personal, and cultural memory and knowledge, and they enable the articulation of self-identity in symbolic ways. The transmission and reproduction of traditional know-how are essential for safeguarding, valorising, and renovating these cultural products.

The collaborative, slow, manual, additive, and non-innovative nature of craftsmanship encompasses its cultural value in apprenticeship. Craftsmanship is performative, corporeal, relational, multisensorial, and rooted in learning and making with others. Its empirical nature is based on methods such as learning by doing, trial and error, and pregnant mistake.

Through the combination of old crafts techniques with cutting-edge new technologies, new dimensions and opportunities emerge for the preservation and restoration of cultural goods, as well as for novel, high-quality products and services and the creation of new professions. The use of XR technologies aims to integrate design and fabrication; cumulative knowledge and intelligent processing; slow manufacturing to immediate making; local production to global distribution, technology, and tradition.

Creative@Hubs aims to extend craftsmanship and apprenticeship by exploring how digital toolkits, can facilitate crafts professionals to design and produce cultural goods and artefacts. Cutting-edge technologies, such as image recognition and machine learning (ML) application to detect material characteristics, knowledge representation schemas of 3D models, authoring tools inserted in VR and XR environments can assist and ease both the training of craftspeople and the creation process of high-quality goods and services, while

Blockchain could be used to enable the exploitation of pre-existing and new assets for protecting intellectual property rights and enhancing circulation.

As a result, crafts would be extended from collective to shared, from hands-on to interconnected, from cumulative to outspread. Their local character will be replaced by ubiquity. Applying digital technologies in a pervasive and explainable way can be the key that allows craft training to become attainable; production to be less challenging and exploitation to restore crafts economic viability. In the new condition of digital craftsmanship, crafts are transformed from a reductive process into a productive one. Our past, the culture of slow, embodied, conscious, collective knowledge, with our future, where technologies and tools can enable us to reconnect to the meaningful and lasting *Mitsein* (Being-with), that is, being and dwelling in the world, but in an evolving, enquiring, inclusive manner.